

Stability and determination of asiaticoside from dry nanoemulsion in rat plasma by LC–MS/MS and its application in a pharmacokinetics study

Wardiyah¹, Santi Purna Sari²

1 Pharmacy Department, Poltekkes Kemenkes Jakarta II, Jln. Hang Jebat III/F3 Kebayoran Baru, Jakarta, Indonesia

2 Faculty of Pharmacy, Universitas Indonesia, Kampus UI, Depok, West Java 16424, Indonesia

3 Centre for Drug Delivery Technology & Vaccine, Faculty of Pharmacy, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, 50300 Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

Corresponding author: Mahdi Jufri (mahdi.jufri@farmasi.ui.ac.id)

Received 2 November 2025 ♦ Accepted 3 February 2026 ♦ Published 18 February 2026

Citation: Wardiyah, Jufri M, Sutriyo, Mun'im A, Zulfakar MH, Sari SP (2026) Stability and determination of asiaticoside from dry nanoemulsion in rat plasma by LC–MS/MS and its application in a pharmacokinetics study. *Pharmacia* 73: 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e176786>

Abstract

This study evaluated the stability and pharmacokinetics of asiaticoside (AS) dry nanoemulsion (AS-DNE) and developed a validated LC–MS/MS method for AS quantification in rat plasma. AS-DNE remained stable over 24 weeks, with minimal changes in moisture content, particle size, and zeta potential. AS degradation was temperature dependent, with the highest loss (6.73%) observed at 40 °C. Plasma samples were prepared by protein precipitation using methanol, with valproic acid used as an internal standard. The method demonstrated excellent linearity (25–2000 ng/mL, $R^2 = 0.9999$), precision (< 7.39%), accuracy (< 11.19%), and recovery (80.95–91.19%), and AS was stable under various tested conditions. Pharmacokinetic studies revealed dose-independent behavior and significantly enhanced oral absorption: AS-DNE reached a peak plasma concentration of 211.32 ng/mL at 15 min, compared with 71.21 ng/mL at 14.4 h for pure AS. These results demonstrate improved bioavailability of AS through dry nanoemulsion formulation.

Keywords

asiaticoside, dry nanoemulsion, LC–MS/MS, pharmacokinetics

Introduction

Centella asiatica (L.) Urban, also known as gotu kola, is a member of the Apiaceae family and is widely distributed across tropical and subtropical regions, particularly in Asia, Africa, and Oceania. Asiaticoside, madecassoside, asiatic acid, and madecassic acid are the primary active metabolites of Gotu Kola, belonging to the ursane-type triterpene group (Kunjumon et al. 2022). These bioactive

compounds contribute to a wide range of pharmacological effects, including neuroprotection by preventing oxidative damage to neurons, as well as antidepressant, anti-inflammatory, and wound-healing properties. Additionally, *C. asiatica* has been recognized for its antiallergic, immunomodulatory, hepatoprotective, and cardioprotective properties, as well as its anti-aging potential. Notably, it has been extensively applied in the treatment of wounds, particularly burns and diabetic ulcers (Lee et

al. 2008; Somboonwong et al. 2012; Sampath and Janardhanam 2013; Hou et al. 2016; Intararuchikul et al. 2019; Razali et al. 2019; Wang et al. 2020).

AS has poor solubility in water, with a value of 0.260 mg/mL (Narisepalli et al. 2023). The main challenge in formulating pharmaceutical preparations, particularly for the oral route, is achieving adequate solubility and dissolution. The solubility factor of the drug significantly influences its absorption in the gastrointestinal tract. Nanoemulsion is one of the methods developed to increase the solubility of a drug substance. In some cases, nanoemulsions are kinetically stable and do not undergo phase separation during several weeks of storage, although particle size increases (Koroleva et al. 2018). Emulsion or nanoemulsion preparations in long-term storage often exhibit stability issues, including droplet aggregation, Ostwald ripening, coalescence, creaming, flocculation, and phase separation (Jang et al. 2006; Singh et al. 2017). Dry emulsion preparation is one way to overcome emulsion instability (Jang et al. 2006). Dry emulsion formulations are effective for maintaining the stability of water-insoluble or unstable active ingredients that are sensitive to light or prone to oxidation (Dollo et al. 2003; El-Messery et al. 2020). Dry emulsions are designed to address the limitations of liquid emulsions with respect to physicochemical properties and user compliance. By removing water, they improve stability, reduce the risk of chemical degradation, and avoid physical issues such as phase separation. This absence of water also shields active ingredients from environmental factors such as light, heat, and oxygen, thereby extending shelf life and maintaining their effectiveness (Ponphaiboon et al. 2024). Drying of emulsions or nanoemulsions can be achieved by spray drying or freeze-drying, which helps prevent oxidation of the preparation. In spray drying, a carrier material, such as maltodextrin, is added to prevent agglomeration of the nanoemulsion during drying (Steiner et al. 2022). One of the objectives of this study was to develop stable and effective dry nanoemulsions using a simple method suitable for pharmaceutical applications. The dry nanoemulsions were prepared by converting liquid oil-in-water (O/W) emulsions into dry powders through adsorption onto solid carriers. Although various carrier agents have been explored for producing dry nanoemulsions, maltodextrin remains a widely favored choice due to its affordability and excellent reconstitution properties.

The pharmacokinetic profile of AS, administered orally to rats at 200 mg/kg, indicated very low bioavailability (1.86%). This result is related to the incomplete absorption of AS, which is thought to be associated with its solubility in water (Liu et al. 2010; Hengjumrut et al. 2018).

Although AS has been widely studied, its oral bioavailability and pharmacokinetic profile remain limited. This study provides new insights into the pharmacokinetics of AS delivered via a dry nanoemulsion, which may enhance systemic exposure and formulation stability. Hence, AS formulations must be developed to improve the compound's characteristics and pharmacokinetic profile.

Characterizing the preliminary pharmacokinetic properties of AS is crucial to the drug's development. Therefore, developing, validating, and applying bioanalytical methods are essential for AS pharmacokinetic studies in drug discovery. LC-MS/MS analysis provides higher sensitivity and faster pharmacokinetic data assessment (Van Eckhaut et al. 2009; Seger and Salzmann 2020). However, the analytical method for biosamples must be validated to ensure reliable and accurate bioanalytical results.

Materials and methods

Materials

AS standard (98% purity) was obtained from PT EBM Sain-tifik dan Teknologi, Bandung, Indonesia, while AS (95% purity) was purchased as an active ingredient from New Natural Biotechnology Co. Ltd., Shanghai, China. Sucrose ester (SE) was sourced from Wuxi Vland Biotech Co., Ltd., China. Sodium caseinate (SC) and maltodextrin (MD) (DE 4–7) were acquired from Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, USA. Virgin coconut oil (VCO) was procured from PT Trivico, Indonesia. Absolute ethanol, ammonium acetate, acetonitrile, and HPLC-grade methanol were obtained from Merck, Germany. All other solvents and chemicals were of analytical grade and sourced from local vendors.

Animals

Sprague-Dawley male rats (230 ± 20 g) were obtained from CV Kencana, Bandung, Indonesia, for this study. The rats were acclimatized for two weeks at the animal facility of the Faculty of Pharmacy, Universitas Indonesia, under standard temperature conditions (25 ± 2 °C), with free access to food and water. At the end of each experiment, the animals were euthanized using a lethal dose of ketamine. The research protocol was approved by the Health Research Ethics Committee, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Indonesia.

Methods

Preparation method of nanoemulsion and dry nanoemulsion of asiaticoside

The nanoemulsion formulation consisted of VCO (13.55% w/w) as the oil phase, SE (2.5% w/w, HLB 3) as the surfactant, and SC (2% w/w) as the co-surfactant. This formulation was optimized using the Box-Behnken design based on a previous study (Wardiyah et al. 2024). The asiaticoside nanoemulsion (AS-NE) was prepared in two stages. First, all ingredients were blended using a high-speed homogenizer, followed by sonication (Pradana and Ritthidej 2023). The preparation process began by heating VCO to 70 °C and adding SE as the oil-phase surfactant. SC was dissolved in water, whereas AS was dissolved in absolute ethanol prior to incorporation into the oil phase. The water phase was then added dropwise to the oil phase. Pre-homogenization

was conducted at 5,000 rpm for 5 minutes using a low-speed homogenizer. The speed was then increased to 10,000 rpm for another 5 minutes. Finally, AS-NE was further homogenized using a probe sonicator at 40% amplitude and 15 W for five minutes (Wardiyah et al. 2024).

The drying process was based on a previous study (Wardiyah et al. 2025). According to the total solid weight, this dry nanoemulsion had a 10% matrix content. Following nanoemulsion formation, the spray-drying procedure was completed. After dissolving maltodextrin in water, it was added to the resulting nanoemulsion while continuously stirring at 5,000 rpm. A Büchi Mini Spray Dryer (model B-290) was used to dry the homogenized mixture. The aspirator rate was 100%, the pump flow was 25%, the inlet temperature was 120 °C, and the flow rate was 5 mL/min. Several crucial parameters, including inlet temperature, aspirator rate, pump flow, and nozzle cleanliness, were consistently maintained to produce high-throughput and repeatable products. After spray drying, the nanoemulsion powder was stored at room temperature in a covered, light-proof container.

Stability testing

The stability of asiaticoside dry nanoemulsion (AS-DNE) was determined under three different conditions: 8 ± 2 °C, 25 ± 2 °C, and 40 ± 2 °C, with relative humidity maintained for 0, 4, 8, 12, and 24 weeks. The samples were packed in tightly sealed vials and protected from light. The evaluation included the polydispersity index (PDI), particle size (D90), zeta potential, moisture content, and asiaticoside content.

PDI, particle size (D90), and zeta potential were analyzed using a particle size analyzer (PSA) at a scattering angle of 173° and a temperature of 25 °C. Samples were prepared by weighing 20 mg of dry asiaticoside nanoemulsion and dispersing it in 10 mL of distilled water. This sample was used to measure zeta potential. A further 0.1 mL was collected and diluted to 10 mL with distilled water for PDI and particle size measurements.

Moisture content was investigated using a moisture balance analyzer by weighing 0.5 g of sample heated with a halogen lamp until the temperature reached 105 °C. The evaluation results were recorded after the sample reached a constant weight. The study was carried out in triplicate.

AS content was investigated using HPLC. A sample equivalent to 5 mg of asiaticoside was weighed and dissolved in 25 mL of methanol in a volumetric flask. The sample solution was sonicated in a bath sonicator for 60 minutes. Subsequently, 0.5 mL of the sample solution was taken and diluted with the mobile phase to a final volume of 5 mL. The resulting solution was filtered through a 0.22 µm nylon membrane filter and analyzed by HPLC at 210 nm.

Analytical method for stability testing

A Shimadzu SPD-20A liquid chromatography system equipped with a UV-Vis detector (Kyoto, Japan) was used for quantitative stability analysis. Chromatographic separation was performed using a Zorbax Eclipse Plus C18

column (4.6 × 250 mm, 5 µm) from Agilent (California, USA). Quantitative analysis of AS was conducted using a reversed-phase HPLC system. The mobile phase consisted of acetonitrile and water (28:72 v/v), with a flow rate of 0.9 mL/min. The oven temperature was ambient, the detection wavelength was set at 210 nm, the injection volume was 10 µL, and the total run time was 12 minutes.

LC-MS/MS bioanalytical method development

The LC-MS/MS method was developed and validated to study the pharmacokinetic profiles of AS and AS-DNE using an LC-MS/MS XEVO TQD system equipped with an autosampler (Waters, Massachusetts, USA). Chromatographic separation of AS and the internal standard (IS; valproic acid) was achieved using an Agilent Zorbax SB-C18 column (5 µm, 2.1 × 150 mm). The mobile phase consisted of ammonium acetate (1 mM) and methanol (20:80, v/v) and was operated in isocratic mode. The flow rate was set at 0.15 mL/min, the oven temperature at 35 °C, the injection volume at 10 µL, and the total run time at 5 minutes.

MS conditions

The mass spectrometer was operated in negative-ion mode using electrospray ionization (ESI). Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) transitions were set at m/z 957.35 → 469.07 for AS and m/z 143.03 → 143.03 for the IS. Electrospray parameters included a capillary voltage of 3.50 kV and a source temperature of 350 °C. The cone and desolvation gas flow rates were 50 L/h and 650 L/h, respectively, with a cone voltage of 56 V. The collision energy was set at 38 V, while the entrance and exit potentials were 0.2 V and 1.5 V, respectively. The multiplier voltage was maintained at 750 V.

Standard solutions, calibration, and quality control samples

Stock solutions (1.0 mg/mL) were prepared by separately dissolving 10 mg of AS and 10 mg of IS in 10 mL of methanol. Calibration standards were prepared by spiking blank rat plasma with freshly prepared working solutions to yield final concentrations of 25, 50, 100, 500, 1,000, and 2,000 ng/mL. Quality control (QC) samples were prepared in the same manner to obtain the lower limit of quantitation (LLOQ), low-quality control (LQC), medium-quality control (MQC), and high-quality control (HQC) samples, with nominal concentrations of 25, 75, 1,000, and 1,600 ng/mL, respectively.

Sample preparation

A 100 µL aliquot of rat plasma was transferred into a 1.5-mL Eppendorf tube, followed by the addition of 20 µL of valproic acid working solution (1,000 ng/mL) as the IS. Subsequently, 200 µL of methanol was added as a deproteinizing agent, and the mixture was vortexed for 60 seconds. Protein precipitation with methanol was selected due to its simplicity, high recovery, and minimal matrix interference in AS analysis. The samples were allowed to stand at room temperature for 1 h before centrifugation at 10,000 rpm for

10 minutes. After centrifugation, 150 μL of the supernatant was carefully transferred into a clean test tube and then transferred into a 96-well autosampler vial plate. A 10 μL aliquot was injected into the LC–MS/MS system for analysis.

Method validation

The LC–MS/MS method was validated in accordance with the Bioanalytical Method Validation guidelines issued by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the European Medicines Agency (EMA). Validation parameters included selectivity, linearity, sensitivity, accuracy, precision, recovery, matrix effects, stability, and dilution integrity. The LLOQ was defined as the minimum concentration detectable in plasma samples. Selectivity was evaluated by analyzing blank plasma samples without AS. Calibration curves were constructed by plotting the analyte-to-IS peak area ratio. Intraday and interday accuracy and precision were assessed. Acceptance criteria for accuracy required deviations within 15% of nominal concentrations for three QC levels and within 20% at the LLOQ. Precision limits were set at $\pm 15\%$ coefficient of variation (CV) for QC samples and $\pm 20\%$ at the LLOQ (FDA 2018; EMA 2022).

System suitability

The system suitability test was conducted before sample analysis began. It was performed by injecting 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ AS and 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ valproic acid solutions into the LC–MS/MS system. The test was performed five times, and the retention time, peak area, and peak area ratio (PAR) values were recorded. System suitability was assessed based on the precision of the five tests, expressed as the coefficient of variation (% CV).

Selectivity

Chromatographic responses of six lots of blank rat plasma were compared with those of LLOQ- and IS-spiked blank plasma to evaluate method selectivity.

Calibration curve and the LLOQ

Calibration standards were prepared by spiking blank rat plasma with working standard solutions and the IS. Based on preliminary studies, a calibration curve with a linear range of 25–2000 ng/mL was established. For each analytical run, calibration curves were generated by plotting back-calculated concentrations against nominal concentrations. Linearity was evaluated using linear regression with appropriate weighting. The LLOQ was considered acceptable when five replicates of the lowest calibration standard exhibited accuracy and precision deviations of less than 20%.

Accuracy and precision

The accuracy and precision of intraday and interday measurements were assessed using five replicates at four QC levels within a single assay and across three consecutive validation days.

Recovery

Recovery was assessed by comparing the peak areas of extracted LQC, MQC, and HQC samples (75, 1000, and 1600 ng/mL) with those of post-extraction spiked samples. The recovery percentage for both the analyte and IS was determined by dividing the peak areas obtained from the extracted samples by those from the post-extraction spiked samples.

Matrix effect

Peak areas of the analyte in extracted blank plasma were compared with those obtained from clean standard solutions at corresponding concentrations to determine the matrix influence of rat plasma on AS analysis. Three replicates of six plasma samples at two QC levels (LQC and HQC) were used to assess matrix effects.

Stability

The stability of AS in rat plasma was evaluated under three conditions: short-term stability (0, 6, and 24 h at room temperature), post-preparative stability (0 and 24 h in an autosampler at room temperature), and freeze–thaw stability (three cycles between $-20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and room temperature). Stability analysis was conducted using three replicates of QC samples at two concentration levels.

Partial validation

Established valid analytical methods can be modified through partial validation. Partial validation can be achieved by assessing accuracy and precision, thereby approaching full validation. The chromatographic conditions used in partial validation were identical to those used in full validation. Analytical parameters partially validated included linearity, LLOQ, precision, and accuracy. A solution of AS in rat plasma at concentrations corresponding to the calibration curve, LLOQ, LQC, MQC, and HQC was prepared. Furthermore, extraction was carried out as described in the sample preparation procedure.

Pharmacokinetic study

The pharmacokinetic study was performed in animals (Sprague–Dawley male rats) procured from CV Kencana, Bandung, Indonesia. The animals were housed at $25 \pm 2\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $50 \pm 15\%$ relative humidity and were subjected to a 12-h light/dark cycle. The study received approval from the Health Research Ethics Committee of Dr. Cipto Mangunkusumo National Hospital, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Indonesia (Protocol No. KET-851/UN2.FI/ETIK/PPM/00.02/2024), issued on 14 June 2024. Following a 7-day quarantine period, the animals were randomly divided into two groups. Five rats received AS-DNE at a dose equivalent to 100 mg/kg AS orally after an overnight fast. Another group ($n = 5$) received AS orally (100 mg/kg) in a 0.3% CMC solution. Blood samples were collected at predetermined time points (0.25, 0.75, 1.5, 3, 6, 12, 24,

30, and 48 h) from the retro-orbital plexus under diethyl ether anesthesia and placed in heparinized tubes. At each time point, 0.2 mL of blood was withdrawn and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 min to separate plasma. Plasma samples were stored at -20°C until analysis. Noncompartmental modeling was used to calculate the relevant pharmacokinetic parameters of AS and AS-DNE.

Data analysis

SPSS version 27.0 was used for statistical analyses. Levene's test was applied to assess the homogeneity of variances. Differences between AS and AS-DNE in pharmacokinetic parameters were evaluated using analysis of variance (ANOVA). When ANOVA indicated significant differences, Tukey's test was used for pairwise comparisons among groups.

Results and discussion

Stability of AS dry nanoemulsion

The spray-drying process was carried out after obtaining the optimal nanoemulsion formula from the Box–Behnken design results (Wardiyah et al. 2024). The inlet temperature for the spray-drying process was 120°C . The carrier used in the spray-drying process was maltodextrin DE 4–7 at a concentration of 10% of the total solids. Maltodextrin, which is highly water soluble, can significantly reduce dispersion viscosity, thereby supporting atomization and drying. Using less than 10% maltodextrin causes many components of the material to adhere to the walls of the spray-drying chamber, resulting in poor drying performance. Conversely, using maltodextrin at high concentrations can cause agglomeration (Sansone et al. 2011). Maltodextrin stabilizes and protects active substances that are unstable during heating. Maltodextrin significantly protects the drug by retaining heat absorbed during drying and storage. The addition of maltodextrin increases the recovery of spray-drying products because it prevents product mass from sticking to the walls of the chamber dryer and cyclone, which can reduce the amount of dry product collected (Pradana and Ritthidej 2023).

Stability testing of pharmaceutical dosage forms is a crucial stage in the drug acceptance process, as it assesses the quality of pharmaceutical products over time under various environmental conditions. Stability testing is conducted to evaluate the impact of storage conditions on potential changes in the characteristics of AS dry nanoemulsion, particularly due to temperature fluctuations. Indonesia is classified as a Zone IVb country under the ASEAN Guidelines, with storage conditions generally set at $30 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 75 \pm 5% relative humidity. For accelerated stability testing, conditions are set at $40 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a relative humidity of 75 \pm 5% (ASEAN 2013). In this study, storage conditions for the stability testing of AS content in dry nanoemulsion were maintained at three temperatures: $8 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, $25 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $40 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, with relative humidity held constant.

Moisture content stability of AS dry nanoemulsion

The results showed that the moisture content of the dry nanoemulsion increased across the three temperatures, indicating an upward trend. However, the moisture content over 24 weeks remained consistently below 3%. The increase in moisture content occurs because the dry nanoemulsion is obtained by spray drying, during which water molecules are removed from the nanoemulsion system, causing AS to exhibit increased hygroscopicity. In addition, the use of a maltodextrin matrix in the formulation can further increase hygroscopicity (Wang et al. 2015; Hariadi et al. 2024).

Statistical analysis revealed that both storage temperature and storage duration significantly affected the moisture content of the dried nanoemulsion ($p < 0.05$). However, the interaction between temperature and storage time did not significantly affect moisture content ($p > 0.05$). Temperature can influence water evaporation from the dried nanoemulsion. The evaporation rate is proportional to temperature and can lead to significant changes in moisture content. At lower temperatures (8°C), the evaporation rate is reduced, resulting in more stable moisture content (Fig. 1).

Storage time also influences moisture content due to factors such as water vapor diffusion and gradual changes in the preparation matrix. The absence of an interaction effect between temperature and time suggests that temperature has a greater influence on moisture content than storage duration. Thus, although moisture content varied across storage times, temperature exerted a more pronounced effect than the combined influence of temperature and time.

Particle size, PDI, and zeta potential stability of AS dry nanoemulsion

Particle size stability was evaluated to determine physical changes in the dry nanoemulsion powder of AS. Initial measurements yielded a D90 value of 282.33 ± 11.93 nm. After 24 weeks of storage at room temperature, the D90 value increased to 296.67 ± 11.24 nm. During cold and high-temperature storage, particle size decreased. Moisture content can influence particle size. However, the D90 values were not statistically significantly different ($p > 0.05$). Particle size stability remained unchanged under all storage conditions over the 24-week period. Therefore, temperature and storage time had no significant effect on the particle size stability of AS dry nanoemulsion. This result is consistent with moisture content stability, as the interaction between temperature and storage time did not significantly affect moisture content.

Particle size heterogeneity is expressed by the polydispersity index (PDI) (Mazonde et al. 2020). Under initial conditions, the PDI value was 0.323 ± 0.028 . After 24 weeks of storage, PDI values increased at all three temperatures, reaching 0.488 ± 0.058 at $8 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, 0.566 ± 0.025 at $25 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, and 0.592 ± 0.036 at $40 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$. PDI values differed significantly based on storage temperature, storage time, and their interaction ($p < 0.05$). Prolonged storage and elevated temperatures can increase PDI due to particle aggregation and coalescence. A low PDI indicates a

Figure 1. Profile of asiaticoside moisture content, particle size, PDI, and zeta potential stability in dry nanoemulsion during 24 weeks of storage.

more uniform particle size distribution and greater system stability due to uniform surface energy, which reduces aggregation and coalescence (Danaei et al. 2018).

After 24 weeks of storage, zeta potential values decreased at all temperatures. The initial zeta potential was -51.4 ± 0.7 mV and decreased to -38.6 ± 0.3 mV, -40.9 ± 1.3 mV, and -33.8 ± 0.5 mV, respectively. These changes may result from chemical alterations, such as surfactant decomposition or the formation of charged molecules (Li et al. 2020). Zeta potential reflects electrostatic stability, with values greater than ± 30 mV indicating sufficient repulsive forces to prevent particle aggregation (Yahya et al. 2022). After 24 weeks, the dry nanoemulsion remained relatively stable at all three temperatures. Statistical analysis showed that temperature alone did not significantly affect zeta potential ($p > 0.05$), whereas storage time did ($p < 0.05$). The interaction between temperature and time was significant ($p < 0.05$), indicating that this interaction influenced changes in zeta potential.

Stability of AS in dry nanoemulsion

The results showed that AS content in the dry nanoemulsion decreased after storage at three temperatures for 24 weeks. The initial AS content was 99.69%. After 24 weeks, AS content decreased to 95.24% under cold storage, 97.49%

at room temperature, and 92.98% under high-temperature storage. The greatest reduction occurred at elevated temperatures (Fig. 2). At 8 °C and 40 °C, significant differences were observed at weeks 12 and 24 compared with initial values ($p < 0.05$). At 25 °C, a significant difference was observed only at week 24. These findings indicate that stability was higher at 25 °C than at 8 °C or 40 °C during storage. Therefore, storage of AS dry nanoemulsion at 25 ± 2 °C is recommended.

Figure 2. Stability of AS content in dry nanoemulsion during 24 weeks of storage.

Data analysis demonstrated that both temperature and storage time significantly affected AS content ($p < 0.05$). Significant reductions were observed between 12 and 24

weeks compared with initial values ($p < 0.05$), whereas no significant difference was observed after 8 weeks ($p > 0.05$).

Stability testing at 40 ± 2 °C showed a 6.7% reduction in AS content, which can be attributed to thermal degradation. These findings are consistent with previous studies reporting decreased AS levels in film-forming dispersions after shorter storage durations at high temperatures (Monton et al. 2018). Similar results were reported by Puttarak et al., who observed degradation of glycoside compounds (asiaticoside and madecassoside) exceeding 15% within four weeks under high-temperature storage, even under light-protected conditions (Puttarak et al. 2016). These findings indicate that increasing temperature accelerates AS degradation. Instability of AS is attributed to glycoside decomposition through hydrolysis under elevated temperatures (Puttarak et al. 2016; Monton et al. 2018). Based on these results, AS formulated as a dry nanoemulsion exhibits greater heat stability than AS in unformulated extracts.

Bioanalysis method validation

The bioanalytical method used was liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry (LC–MS/MS). Bioanalytical validation is essential to ensure method performance and data reliability. Validation parameters were evaluated in accordance with the Guideline on Bioanalytical Method Validation and Study Sample Analysis issued by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) and the US FDA. The validation parameters tested were selectivity, specificity, matrix effect, calibration curve (response function), range (lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) to upper limit of quantification (ULOQ)), accuracy, precision, carryover, dilution integrity, stability, and reinjection reproducibility (FDA 2018; EMA 2022).

Optimization of LC–MS/MS conditions

Optimization of LC–MS/MS conditions aimed to achieve symmetrical peaks and adequate resolution through repeated testing. Various mobile phase compositions and chromatographic columns were evaluated to determine optimal separation conditions. The optimal mobile phase consisted of 1 mM ammonium acetate and methanol (20:80, v/v), providing improved resolution and peak symmetry with retention times of 2–3 minutes under reversed-phase conditions. Valproic acid was used as the internal standard. The mobile phase was delivered isocratically at a flow rate of 0.15 mL/min, with a total run time of 5 minutes. Chromatographic separation yielded a sharp AS peak at 2.50 minutes. The chromatographic profile of asiaticoside in rat plasma is presented in Fig. 3. This result confirms clear peak separation and absence of interfering signals.

The tuning process was conducted to identify ionization mode and mass spectrometric conditions that yielded the highest sensitivity. Negative electrospray ionization (ESI) provided superior sensitivity, consistent with previous reports (Liu et al. 2010). Parameters such as cone voltage and collision energy were optimized to generate precursor and product ions. For AS, the optimized cone voltage and collision energy were 56 V and 38 V, respectively.

Figure 3. AS chromatogram in plasma.

Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) was employed for detection. The mass spectra of AS and valproic acid exhibited parent ions at m/z 957.35 and 143.03, respectively. Fragmentation produced daughter ions at m/z 469.07 for AS and 143.03 for valproic acid. These results are consistent with previously reported transitions for AS ($957.4 \rightarrow 469.3$ m/z) (Liu et al. 2010).

System suitability

System suitability was evaluated using five replicate injections of AS and valproic acid. The results showed that peak area coefficients of variation for both compounds were $< 2\%$ (Table 1), indicating that the chromatographic system was suitable for analysis.

Table 1. System suitability for asiaticoside and valproic acid.

No	Asiaticoside		Valproic acid	
	Peak area	Retention time (minutes)	Peak area	Retention time (minutes)
1	26274	2.49	369775	2.36
2	25839	2.49	374096	2.36
3	26577	2.50	377864	2.35
4	26384	2.49	373981	2.35
5	26242	2.50	371564	2.35
Mean	26263.2	2.49	373456	2.35
St. deviation	270.91	0.01	3051.44	0.01
% CV	1.03	0.22	0.82	0.23

Selectivity

Fig. 4 displays chromatograms of the blank matrix and samples spiked with plasma at LLOQ, IS, LQC, MQC, and HQC. The retention times for detecting AS and IS, without interference from plasma matrix components, were 2.49 and 2.35 minutes, respectively, demonstrating that the method was sufficiently sensitive and selective to enable effective extraction.

Calibration curve and LLOQ

The linearity of the calibration curve was evaluated five times across three different occasions. The linear range for the AS calibration curve was 25–2000 ng/mL, and a correlation coefficient of 0.9999 indicated a good fit. Linear regression best described the analyte concentration–detector response

Figure 4. Chromatograms of **a.** Blank plasma; **b.** Internal standard; **c.** LLOQ; **d.** Low-quality control (LQC); **e.** Medium-quality control (MQC); **f.** High-quality control (HQC).

relationship using $1/x^2$ least-squares weighting (Fig. 5). The LLOQ was 25 ng/mL. Deviations of back-calculated concentrations for all calibration curve points and the LLOQ from their nominal values were within 15% and 20%, respectively. The correlation coefficient for the calibration curve was comparable to that reported for AS by Liu et al. (2010). The LLOQs were 38 ng/mL, which exceeded 25 ng/mL.

Figure 5. Calibration curve for AS in plasma ($n = 5$).

Accuracy and precision

Accuracy and precision were evaluated at LLOQ, LQC, MQC, and HQC levels of 25, 75, 1000, and 2000 ng/mL, respectively, with the results summarized in Table 2. Intra-assay coefficients of variation (CVs) ranged from

2.24% to 7.39%, while percent relative errors (REs) ranged from 2.08% to 11.19%. Inter-assay CVs ranged from 1.36% to 3.38%, with REs ranging from -4.96% to 6.48%. Despite these variations, accuracy and precision values were within acceptable limits. The method's accuracy and precision for AS determination met the criteria outlined in US FDA and EMA guidelines, confirming its reliability and reproducibility across the tested concentration range.

Table 2. Intra-assay and inter-assay accuracy and precision of AS in plasma ($n = 6$).

Assay	Nominal concentration (ng/mL)	Observed concentration \pm SD (ng/mL)	Precision (% CV)	Accuracy % RE
Intra-assay	25	24.98 \pm 1.85	7.39	2.08
	75	80.90 \pm 1.81	2.24	10.20
	1000	1088.37 \pm 26.21	2.41	11.19
	1600	1735.96 \pm 74.20	4.27	10.85
Inter-assay	25	23.26 \pm 0.55	2.36	-4.96
	75	77.41 \pm 2.62	3.38	5.45
	1000	992.95 \pm 13.47	1.36	1.45
	1600	166.57 \pm 49.20	2.95	6.48

Recovery and matrix effect

Recovery was assessed at three QC concentrations: 75, 1000, and 1600 ng/mL (Table 3). The recovery rates for asiaticoside

were 80.95%, 88.26%, and 91.19%, with % CV values of 7.36%, 1.47%, and 2.90%, respectively. Although these recovery rates were lower than those reported in previous studies (96.0%–101.2%) (Liu et al. 2010), the % CV values below 15% indicate that the analytical method remains reliable and reproducible. For valproic acid, recovery rates ranged from 93.24% to 100.44%, with % CV values below 5%.

Table 3. Assessment of the recovery of AS in plasma.

Compound	Nominal concentration (ng/mL)	Recovery (%)	CV (%)
Asiaticoside	75	80.95	7.36
	1000	88.26	1.47
	1600	91.19	2.90
Valproic acid	75	93.24	4.22
	1000	100.44	1.04
	1600	98.40	2.00

Matrix effects, which refer to changes in analyte response caused by interfering components in the sample matrix (Van Eeckhaut et al. 2009), were evaluated at the LQC and HQC levels using three replicates across six plasma matrices (Table 4). The % CV values for LQC ranged from 2.19% to 12.78%, whereas those for HQC ranged from 0.77% to 13.06%. With CV values below 15%, the results demonstrate that the method consistently and reproducibly recovered asiaticoside from plasma following extraction. Furthermore, the matrix effect of rat plasma on the bioanalytical method for asiaticoside was not significant (FDA 2018; EMA 2022).

Table 4. Assessment of the matrix effect of AS in plasma.

Nominal concentration (ng/mL)	Plasma	Matrix effect (%)	CV (%)
75	A	99.93	12.78
	B	98.38	3.20
	C	92.22	5.42
	D	109.85	3.47
	E	102.51	2.19
	F	105.20	5.23
1600	A	112.36	0.77
	B	102.25	13.06
	C	104.23	8.40
	D	110.02	1.82
	E	104.72	2.90
	A	103.82	2.49

Dilution integrity

In the dilution integrity test, at least one concentration exceeded the ULOQ. For this study, concentrations of $2 \times$ ULOQ, ULOQ, and $\frac{1}{2}$ ULOQ were tested. Each concentration was evaluated in five replicates to determine whether it could be measured accurately and precisely within the calibration range. Accuracy, calculated as % RE, ranged from 8.50% to 11.94%. The % CV, reflecting test precision, was 7.80%, 1.33%, and 5.11% for concentrations of $\frac{1}{2}$ ULOQ, ULOQ, and $2 \times$ ULOQ, respectively (Table 5). These results demonstrate that the method is accurate,

precise, and reproducible for diluted samples with asiaticoside concentrations exceeding 1600 ng/mL, as indicated by % CV and % RE values < 15%, in compliance with US FDA and EMA guidelines (FDA 2018; EMA 2022).

Table 5. Dilution integrity of AS.

Nominal concentration (ng/mL)	Measured concentration (ng/mL)		
	Mean \pm SD	CV (%)	RE (%)
800	849.60 \pm 66.23	7.80	8.50
1600	1753.07 \pm 23.27	1.33	11.94
3200	3414.30 \pm 174.57	5.11	9.01

Stability

AS was evaluated for short-term stability, freeze/thaw stability, and autosampler stability in three replicates at two QC levels. Results are shown in Table 6. The CV and RE values for all stability conditions tested were < 7% and < 15%, respectively (Table 6). These findings are consistent with a previous study on method development and validation for AS (Liu et al. 2010). The results indicate that AS was stable under all conditions expected to be encountered during use of this bioanalytical method. The stability of asiaticoside reduces the need for stringent precautions during laboratory handling and analytical procedures.

Table 6. Stability of AS in plasma.

Stability test	Nominal concentration (ng/mL)	Measured concentration (ng/mL)		
		Mean \pm SD	CV (%)	RE (%)
Short-term (6 h, RT)	75	66.40 \pm 2.11	3.19	-9.55
	1600	1562.15 \pm 57.53	3.68	-0.25
Long-term (7 days, -20 °C)	75	74.84 \pm 2.39	3.19	1.94
	1600	1534.22 \pm 116.20	7.57	-0.32
Freeze and thaw (-20 °C to RT)	75	71.32 \pm 4.35	6.10	-2.85
	1600	1423.07 \pm 13.29	0.93	-9.13
Autosampler (24 h, RT)	75	64.50 \pm 2.61	4.05	-12.14
	1600	1762.32 \pm 46.20	2.62	-12.54

Partial validation

Due to changes in the analytical method, a partial validation was conducted. Specifically, the sample matrix was changed from human plasma, which was used in the full method validation, to rat plasma for the bioavailability study of asiaticoside.

The parameters tested in this partial validation included linearity, LLOQ, precision, and accuracy. The linearity test yielded a linear regression equation of $y = 0.0002x + 0.0015$, with an R^2 value of 0.9987 (Fig. 6). The linearity results indicated that no data points exceeded $\pm 15\%$ of the % RE. For LLOQ concentrations, the % RE did not exceed $\pm 20\%$, meeting the required criteria.

The LLOQ was set at 25 ng/mL and was tested in five replicates (Table 7). The % RE and CV values met the accuracy and precision criteria for this concentration, remaining within $\pm 20\%$. Subsequently, the analyte concentration was reduced to 12 ng/mL and tested in five replicates. The results indicated that the % RE and CV values exceeded the $\pm 20\%$

Figure 6. Calibration curve for AS in plasma (n = 5) for partial validation.

Table 7. Determination of LLOQ in partial validation.

Nominal concentration (ng/mL)	Measured concentration (ng/mL)		
	Mean ± SD	CV (%)	RE (%)
25	26.33 ± 3.20	11.48	7.6
12	100.57 ± 52.17	51.87	739.48

threshold, failing to meet the accuracy and precision criteria. Therefore, the LLOQ established in this partial validation is consistent with that determined in the full validation.

Partial validation was conducted to assess accuracy and precision at LLOQ, LQC, MQC, and HQC concentrations. The % CV values ranged from 5.70% to 12.14%, and the % RE values were below 15% (Table 8). These results demonstrate that accuracy and precision met the acceptable criteria outlined in US FDA and EMA guidelines. Moreover, the findings confirm that the accuracy and precision of the method were consistent with those achieved during full validation of the analytical method (FDA 2018; EMA 2022).

Table 8. Accuracy and precision in partial validation.

Nominal concentration (ng/mL)	Measured concentration (ng/mL)		
	Mean ± SD	CV (%)	RE (%)
25	24.47 ± 2.64	12.14	-11.20
75	76.76 ± 6.76	8.81	4.56
1000	902.43 ± 51.42	5.70	-7.80
1600	1568.84 ± 138.98	8.86	0.18

Figure 7. Pharmacokinetic profiles of pure asiaticoside (AS) and asiaticoside dry nanoemulsion (AS-DNE) in rat plasma following oral administration.

Pharmacokinetic application

The pharmacokinetic study was conducted using male Sprague–Dawley rats. This study received approval from the Health Research Ethics Committee of RSUP Nasional Dr. Cipto Mangunkusumo, Faculty of Medicine, University of Indonesia, under approval number KET-851/UN2.FI/ETIK/PPM/00.02/2024, issued on 14 June 2024. The study involved two groups of animals: one received pure asiaticoside, and the other received asiaticoside dry nanoemulsion. The administered dose was 100 mg/kg body weight via oral gavage. Samples were collected at 0, 0.25 (15 minutes), 0.75 (45 minutes), 1.5, 3, 6, 12, 24, 30, and 48 h. The pharmacokinetic profiles of both test substances are shown in Fig. 7.

Based on Fig. 7, AS-DNE reached a C_{max} of 211.32 ± 22.66 ng/mL at 0.25 h, compared with 71.21 ± 26.29 ng/mL at 14.40 h for pure AS. These results indicate that asiaticoside in the dry nanoemulsion was absorbed more rapidly than pure asiaticoside. These findings are consistent with the in vitro dissolution test results, in which asiaticoside in the dry nanoemulsion exhibited greater release into the dissolution medium than pure asiaticoside (Wardiyah et al. 2025). This demonstrates that the asiaticoside nanoemulsion formulation significantly enhances solubility, thereby improving the drug absorption process in the body (Rao and Aghav 2014).

Following oral administration, nanoparticles may be absorbed or excreted (Lai et al. 2009), with biodistribution influenced by particle size, preparation method, and physicochemical interactions (Sa et al. 2012). Particles smaller than 50 nm can pass through hepatocytes more readily, whereas larger particles tend to accumulate in the liver and spleen, reducing circulation time (Almeida et al. 2011; Ernsting et al. 2013). Spherical particles are more susceptible to phagocytosis, and nanoparticles with a zeta potential of $\geq \pm 40$ mV are rapidly cleared from the systemic circulation (>90% within 10 minutes) (Champion and Mitragotri 2009; Raza et al. 2017).

The pharmacokinetic results showed nonlinear AUC and C_{max} values. Although the absorption rate increased, the AUC_{0-t} and $AUC_{0-\infty}$ values for the dry nanoemulsion were lower than those for pure asiaticoside (Table 9).

This finding indicates that, although the dry nanoemulsion enhanced initial absorption, total systemic exposure was lower than that of pure asiaticoside. This phenomenon may be attributed to changes in the physical properties and structure of the nanoemulsion following spray drying, which may affect drug dissolution and release behavior. Although AS-DNE enhanced absorption, as reflected by higher C_{max} and shorter T_{max} , the lower AUC values suggest more rapid systemic clearance, potentially due to nanoparticle uptake by the reticuloendothelial system, as reported for lipid-based nanoparticles. This pharmacokinetic behavior is consistent with previous reports describing lipid-based nanoparticles, which often exhibit rapid absorption followed by accelerated clearance due to hepatic and splenic uptake (Ernsting et al. 2013; Raza et al. 2017; Kumar et al. 2023).

Table 9. Pharmacokinetic parameters of asiaticoside and asiaticoside dry nanoemulsion.

Pharmacokinetic parameters	AS	AS-DNE
C_{max} (ng/mL)	71.21 ± 26.29	211.32 ± 22.66
T_{max} (h)	14.40 ± 5.37	0.25 ± 0
AUC_{0-4} (ng.jam/mL)	933.52 ± 302.55	469.74 ± 204.11
$AUC_{0-∞}$ (ng.jam/mL)	1019.79 ± 310.88	473.24 ± 208.60
$t_{1/2}$ (h)	12.60 ± 3.07	8.87 ± 1.75
CL/F (L/H)	25.85 ± 11.73	60.43 ± 31.50

*Analysis with the independent-sample t-test for all parameters showed significantly different results for AS and AS-DNE ($p < 0.05$).

The AUC value is influenced not only by C_{max} but also by the absorption profile. A compound may have a slower but more efficient absorption profile than another, meaning that a compound reaching a lower peak concentration (C_{max}) but releasing the drug more stably and over a longer period can produce a greater AUC. The AUC is calculated as the ratio of dose to clearance. If a compound has a lower clearance, its AUC will be greater. This is also influenced by $t_{1/2}$. Because of a longer $t_{1/2}$, the elimination process of the drug becomes slower, which leads to a larger AUC value due to prolonged drug exposure in the body. The elimination half-life ($t_{1/2}$) of the dry nanoemulsion was shorter than that of pure asiaticoside (12.60 ± 3.07 h), indicating that the dry nanoemulsion formulation had a higher clearance (CL/F) than pure asiaticoside. This increased clearance indicates that the dry nanoemulsion is eliminated more rapidly from systemic circulation. Another factor influencing the AUC value is the volume of distribution (Vd), because a compound with broader tissue distribution but slower release into plasma may exhibit a lower C_{max} but a greater total AUC (Haripriyaa and Suthindhiran 2023; Hedaya 2023).

First-pass metabolism can also influence AUC. For compounds undergoing more extensive first-pass metabolism, bioavailability is reduced even if C_{max} is higher. Several studies have shown that lipid nanoparticles are primarily distributed in the liver and spleen and are rapidly cleared from the bloodstream. This rapid clearance is attributed to opsonization and phagocytosis, which contribute to accelerated nanoparticle elimination (Kumar et al. 2023). The addition of polyethylene glycol (PEG)

to nanoparticles (pegylation) helps prevent opsonization by forming a hydration layer around the nanoparticles, thereby reducing immune recognition and slowing clearance (Yang et al. 2014; Suk et al. 2016; Becicka et al. 2021).

Conventional pharmacokinetic methods, which focus solely on the drug, are not fully applicable to nanocarrier-based drugs, because nanoparticles significantly influence drug interactions within the body. Further studies should address the fate of nanoparticles—whether they accumulate, degrade, or are excreted—and their interactions within biological systems to better understand nanomedicine pharmacokinetics (Raza et al. 2017).

Conclusion

This study focused on the stability and pharmacokinetic analysis of asiaticoside formulated as a dry nanoemulsion, with results highlighting its potential for preclinical drug development. Moisture content of the dry nanoemulsion increased over time but remained below 3% after 24 weeks, with storage temperature significantly influencing these changes. Particle size (D90) remained stable across storage conditions, whereas the polydispersity index increased due to particle aggregation. Zeta potential values decreased over time but remained within electrostatically stable ranges, with both temperature and storage duration influencing these changes.

Asiaticoside content decreased after 24 weeks of storage, with the greatest reduction observed at 40 °C (92.98%), whereas storage at 25 °C provided the highest stability. Degradation at elevated temperatures was attributed to glycoside hydrolysis, although the dry nanoemulsion exhibited greater heat stability than unformulated extracts.

The LC–MS/MS bioanalytical method developed in this study was validated according to international standards and demonstrated excellent selectivity, linearity, accuracy, and precision. The method enabled accurate quantification of asiaticoside at concentrations exceeding 1600 ng/mL, with a quantitation limit lower than that reported for previous methods. Successfully applied in a pharmacokinetic study following a single oral dose of 100 mg/kg asiaticoside in rats, this method supports its use in broader preclinical investigations of asiaticoside and related compounds.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: Protocol no: KET-851/UN2.FI/ETIK/PPM/00.02/2024 issued on 14 June 2024.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

Wardiyah Wardiyah: conceptualization, methodology, visualization, writing original draft preparation; Mahdi Jufri:

conceptualization, methodology, visualization, funding acquisition, writing—review; Sutriyo Sutriyo: methodology, investigation, writing—review and editing; Abdul Mun'im: methodology, writing—review and editing; Mohd Hanif Zulfakar: methodology, writing—review and editing; Santi Purna Sari: data curation, writing—review..

Author ORCIDs

Wardiyah <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9381-9629>

Mohd Hanif Zulfakar <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0547-0370>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Almeida JPM, Chen AL, Foster A, Drezek R (2011) In vivo biodistribution of nanoparticles. *Nanomedicine* 6: 815–835. <https://doi.org/10.2217/nnm.11.79>
- ASEAN (2013) ASEAN Guidelines on Stability Study and Shelf-Life of Traditional Medicines.
- Becicka WM, Bielecki PA, Lorkowski ME, Moon TJ, Zhang Y, Atukorale PU, Covarrubias G, Karathanasis E (2021) The effect of PEGylation on the efficacy and uptake of an immunostimulatory nanoparticle in the tumor immune microenvironment. *Nanoscale Advances* 3: 4961–4972. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1na00308a>
- Champion JA, Mitragotri S (2009) Shape Induced Inhibition of Phagocytosis of Polymer Particles. *Pharmaceutical Research* 26: 244–249. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11095-008-9626-z>
- Danaei M, Dehghankhold M, Ataei S, Hasanzadeh Davarani F, Javanmard R, Dokhani A, Khorasani S, Mozafari MR (2018) Impact of particle size and polydispersity index on the clinical applications of lipidic nanocarrier systems. *Pharmaceutics* 10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics10020057>
- Dollo G, Le Corre P, Guérin A, Chevanne F, Burgot JL, Leverge R (2003) Spray-dried redispersible oil-in-water emulsion to improve oral bioavailability of poorly soluble drugs. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 19: 273–280. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0928-0987\(03\)00134-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0928-0987(03)00134-9)
- Van Eeckhaut A, Lanckmans K, Sarre S, Smolders I, Michotte Y (2009) Validation of bioanalytical LC-MS/MS assays: Evaluation of matrix effects. *Journal of Chromatography B: Analytical Technologies in the Biomedical and Life Sciences* 877: 2198–2207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchromb.2009.01.003>
- El-Messery TM, Altuntas U, Altin G, Özçelik B (2020) The effect of spray-drying and freeze-drying on encapsulation efficiency, in vitro bioaccessibility and oxidative stability of krill oil nanoemulsion system. *Food Hydrocolloids* 106: 105890. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2020.105890>
- EMA (2022) ICH guideline M10 on bioanalytical method validation and study sample analysis Step5. www.ema.europa.eu/contact
- Ernsting MJ, Murakami M, Roy A, Li SD (2013) Factors controlling the pharmacokinetics, biodistribution and intratumoral penetration of nanoparticles. *Journal of Controlled Release* 172: 782–794. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2013.09.013>
- FDA (2018) Bioanalytical Method Validation Guidance for Industry. <https://www.fda.gov/files/drugs/published/Bioanalytical-Method-Validation-Guidance-for-Industry.pdf>
- Hariadi H, Wahyono T, Darniadi S, Maulana H, Nurhadi B, Amien S, Karuniawan A, Khan AA, Aziz T, Alasmari AF (2024) Effect of maltodextrin concentration and drying temperature on the physicochemical characteristics of Sacha inchi (*Plukenetia volubilis*) extract powder. *Italian Journal of Food Science* 36: 74–82. <https://doi.org/10.15586/ijfs.v36i2.2458>
- HariPriyaa M, Suthindhiran K (2023) Pharmacokinetics of nanoparticles: current knowledge, future directions and its implications in drug delivery. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43094-023-00569-y>
- Hedayat MA (2023) *Basic Pharmacokinetics*. 3rd edn. Taylor & Francis, 87–101.
- Hengjumrut P, Anukunwithaya T, Tantisira MH, Tantisira B, Khemawoot P (2018) Comparative pharmacokinetics between madecassoside and asiaticoside presented in a standardised extract of *Centella asiatica*, ECa 233 and their respective pure compound given separately in rats. *Xenobiotica* 48: 18–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00498254.2016.1273562>
- Hou Q, Li M, Lu YH, Liu DH, Li CC (2016) Burn wound healing properties of asiaticoside and madecassoside. *Experimental and Therapeutic Medicine* 12: 1269–1274. <https://doi.org/10.3892/etm.2016.3459>
- Intararuchikul T, Teerapattarakon N, Rodsiri R, Tantisira M, Wohlge-muth G, Fiehn O, Tansawat R (2019) Effects of *Centella asiatica* extract on antioxidant status and liver metabolome of rotenone-treated rats using GC–MS. *Biomedical Chromatography* 33: e4395. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bmc.4395>
- Jang DJ, Jeong EJ, Lee HM, Kim BC, Lim SJ, Kim CK (2006) Improvement of bioavailability and photostability of amlodipine using redispersible dry emulsion. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 28: 405–411. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejps.2006.04.013>
- Koroleva M, Nagovitsina T, Yurtov E (2018) Nanoemulsions stabilized by non-ionic surfactants: Stability and degradation mechanisms. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* 20: 10369–10377. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7cp07626f>
- Kumar M, Kulkarni P, Liu S, Chemuturi N, Shah DK (2023) Nanoparticle biodistribution coefficients: A quantitative approach for understanding

- the tissue distribution of nanoparticles. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews* 194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2023.114708>
- Kunjumon R, Johnson AJ, Baby S (2022) *Centella asiatica*: Secondary metabolites, biological activities and biomass sources. *Phytomedicine Plus* 2: 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phyplu.2021.100176>
- Lai SK, Wang YY, Hanes J (2009) Mucus-penetrating nanoparticles for drug and gene delivery to mucosal tissues. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews* 61: 158–171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2008.11.002>
- Lee J, Jung E, Lee H, Seo Y, Koh J, Park D (2008) Evaluation of the effects of a preparation containing asiaticoside on periocular wrinkles of human volunteers. *International Journal of Cosmetic Science* 30: 167–173. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2494.2008.00440.x>
- Li H, Peng Q, Guo Y, Wang X, Zhang L (2020) Preparation and in vitro and in vivo study of asiaticoside-loaded nanoemulsions and nanoemulsions-based gels for transdermal delivery. *International Journal of Nanomedicine* 15: 3123–3136. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJN.S241923>
- Liu SJ, Liu ZX, Ju WZ, Chen ZY, Xiong NN, Tan HS (2010) Determination of asiaticoside in rat plasma by LC-MS-MS and its application to pharmacokinetics studies. *Chromatographia* 72: 821–825. <https://doi.org/10.1365/s10337-010-1750-3>
- Mazonde P, Khamanga SMM, Walker RB (2020) Design, optimization, manufacture and characterization of Efavirenz-loaded flaxseed oil nanoemulsions. *Pharmaceutics* 12: 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics12090797>
- Monton C, Luprasong C, Suksaeree J, Songsak T (2018) Validated high performance liquid chromatography for simultaneous determination of stability of madecassoside and asiaticoside in film forming polymeric dispersions. *Revista Brasileira de Farmacognosia* 28: 289–293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bjrp.2018.04.003>
- Narisepalli S, Salunkhe SA, Chitkara D, Mittal A (2023) Asiaticoside polymeric nanoparticles for effective diabetic wound healing through increased collagen biosynthesis: In-vitro and in-vivo evaluation. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 631. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2022.122508>
- Ponphaiboon J, Limmatvapirat S, Limmatvapirat C (2024) Development and Evaluation of a Dry Emulsion of Ostrich Oil as a Dietary Supplement. *Foods* 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods13162570>
- Pradana AT, Ritthidej GC (2023) Spray Drying of Asiatic Acid-Palm Oil in Maltodextrin: Improving the Nanoemulsion Characteristics. *International Journal of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology* 19: 21–33. <https://doi.org/10.22034/ijnn.2023.554021.2206>
- Puttarak P, Brantner A, Panichayupakaranant P (2016) Biological activities and stability of a standardized pentacyclic triterpene enriched centella asiatica extract. *Natural Product Sciences* 22: 20–24. <https://doi.org/10.20307/nps.2016.22.1.20>
- Rao MRP, Aghav SS (2014) Spray-dried redispersible emulsion to improve oral bioavailability of itraconazole. *Journal of Surfactants and Detergents* 17: 807–817. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11743-013-1538-1>
- Raza K, Kumar P, Kumar N, Malik R (2017) Pharmacokinetics and bio-distribution of the nanoparticles. In: *Advances in Nanomedicine for the Delivery of Therapeutic Nucleic Acids*. Elsevier Inc., 166–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100557-6.00009-2>
- Razali NNM, Ng CT, Fong LY (2019) Cardiovascular Protective Effects of *Centella asiatica* and Its Triterpenes: A Review. *Planta Medica* 85: 1203–1215. <https://doi.org/10.1055/a-1008-6138>
- Sa LTM, Albernaz M de S, Patricio BF de C, Junior MVE, Coelho BF, Bordim A, Almeida JC, Santos-Oliveira R (2012) Biodistribution of nanoparticles: Initial considerations. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis* 70: 602–604. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2012.06.008>
- Sampath U, Janardhanam VA (2013) Asiaticoside, a trisaccharide triterpene induces biochemical and molecular variations in brain of mice with parkinsonism. *BioMed Central* 2: 23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2047-9158-2-23>
- Sansone F, Mencherini T, Picerno P, D'Amore M, Aquino RP, Lauro MR (2011) Maltodextrin/pectin microparticles by spray drying as carrier for nutraceutical extracts. *Journal of Food Engineering* 105: 468–476. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2011.03.004>
- Seger C, Salzmänn L (2020) After another decade: LC-MS/MS became routine in clinical diagnostics. *Clinical Biochemistry* 82: 2–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinbiochem.2020.03.004>
- Singh Y, Meher JG, Raval K, Khan FA, Chaurasia M, Jain NK, Chourasia MK (2017) Nanoemulsion: Concepts, development and applications in drug delivery. *Journal of Controlled Release* 252: 28–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2017.03.008>
- Somboonwong J, Kankaisre M, Tantisira B, Tantisira MH (2012) Wound healing activities of different extracts of *Centella asiatica* in incision and burn wound models: an experimental animal study. *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine* 12: 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6882-12-103>
- Steiner D, Schumann L V., Bunjes H (2022) Processing of Lipid Nanodispersions into Solid Powders by Spray Drying. *Pharmaceutics* 14: 2464. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics14112464>
- Suk JS, Xu Q, Kim N, Hanes J, Ensign LM (2016) PEGylation as a strategy for improving nanoparticle-based drug and gene delivery. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews* 99: 28–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2015.09.012>
- Wang L, Guo T, Guo Y, Xu Y (2020) Asiaticoside produces an antidepressant-like effect in a chronic unpredictable mild stress model of depression in mice, involving reversion of inflammation and the PKA/pCREB/BDNF signaling pathway. *Molecular Medicine Reports* 22: 2364–2372. <https://doi.org/10.3892/mmr.2020.11305>
- Wang W, Dufour C, Zhou W (2015) Impacts of spray-drying conditions on the physicochemical properties of soy sauce powders using maltodextrin as auxiliary drying carrier. *CYTA - Journal of Food* 13: 548–555. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19476337.2015.1014430>
- Wardiyah W, Jufri M, Sutriyo S, Mun'im A (2025) Characterization and in vitro release testing of asiaticoside dry nanoemulsion prepared by spray drying. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology* 18. <https://doi.org/10.52711/0974-360x.2025.00548>
- Wardiyah W, Jufri M, Sutriyo S, Mun'im A, Hanif Zulfakar M (2024) Development and Optimization of Asiaticoside Nanoemulsion Formulation by Box-Behnken Design. *FARMACIA* 72: 1397–1407. <https://doi.org/10.31925/farmacia.2024.6.19>
- Yahya NA, Wahab RA, Attan N, Hashim SE, Abdul Hamid M, Mohamed Noor N, Abdul Rahman A (2022) Optimization of oil-in-water nanoemulsion system of Ananas comosus peels extract by D-optimal mixture design and its physicochemical properties. *Journal of Dispersion Science and Technology* 43: 302–315. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01932691.2020.1839485>
- Yang Q, Jones SW, Parker CL, Zamboni WC, Bear JE, Lai SK (2014) Evading immune cell uptake and clearance requires PEG grafting at densities substantially exceeding the minimum for brush conformation. *Molecular Pharmaceutics* 11: 1250–1258. <https://doi.org/10.1021/mp400703d>